

Exploring the local and regional dimensions of the Renewable Energy Communities' activation in diverse European institutional contexts

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Abstract

Energy transition is a pivotal challenge for urban and regional development across European territories. Integrating this issue into local policy agendas and spatial planning tools is essential to foster effective engagement of public authorities and local communities in achieving climate neutrality by 2050. Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) are a key tool in climate policy, enabling citizens, civil society organizations, local authorities, and small and medium-sized enterprises to play an active role in the energy supply system. Within RECs, these actors move from being mere consumers to becoming prosumers, thus contributing to more decentralized and democratic energy systems. However, the successful implementation of RECs requires supportive multilevel governance structures and coherent legal and regulatory frameworks to facilitate their development in diverse national, regional, and local contexts.

This paper investigates the role of regional and local authorities, stakeholders, and planning tools in the activation process of RECs within European territories. It analyzes the activation process of different REC configurations by reconstructing the multilevel governance frameworks and exploring the interactions between local, regional and national levels. The work focuses on three case studies, Piedmont (Italy), Andalusia (Spain), Geneva (Switzerland), to illustrate the dynamics of REC creation. This study provides a basis for future research focusing on the interrelationship between energy transition processes and territorial governance frameworks. Empirical evidence suggests that integrated governance arrangements are more effective in aligning spatial planning with climate and energy strategies.

Keywords

Renewable Energy Communities, Spatial planning, Climate policies, Energy transition, European regions

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Introduction

The “just local energy transition” towards sustainable and renewable energy production and consumption patterns is a pivotal challenge for regional development policies in Europe (Otamendi-Irizar et al, 2022). This is because the social and economic benefits of the energy transition can be substantial, and their fair distribution is crucial for guaranteeing all actors equitable access to the opportunities offered by the transition itself. In order to reach energy and climate objectives by 2050 regional and local authorities are key actors (Santopietro & Scorza, 2023). They can drive a fair transition, since they have administrative and political power to develop and implement adequate policy instruments for enhancing energy efficiency and fostering the deployment of local renewable energy sources, as in the case of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs).

RECs as policy instruments

An energy community can be defined as “(...) a way to "organize" collective energy actions around open, democratic participation and governance, and the provision of benefits for the members or the local community” (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020, p. 4, referring to Roberts et al, 2019). Following Baratti, Barbanente & Marzocca (2020), RECs are not merely technical and administrative devices defined and implemented within the renewable energy sector, but social and political processes that develop simultaneously with local energy production in the local social, labour and economic systems, based on the valorisation of local energy potential as a common good and the reduction of energy dependence. From this perspective, energy communities are institutions that can be considered as policy instrument (Le Galès, 2010). Based on the principle of “agreement- and incentive-based instruments”¹, RECs can be approached as instruments of an overall social and environmental policy focusing on local energy transition. RECs’ establishment is based on agreements and RECs’ financial sustainability is often ensured by incentives. Not by chance, they have been in the limelight in Europe, owing to their potential to facilitate a more sustainable, horizontal and distributed energy supply (D’Alpaos & Andreolli, 2021).

According to OIPE (2023), public institutions play a fundamental role in both the establishment of RECs and the generation of economic and social benefits. Several studies highlight the decisive role of state, regional, provincial, and local governments in ensuring the viability and success of REC development and in promoting large investments in distributed renewable energy resources (Parreño-Rodríguez et al, 2023). Furthermore, Dudka et al (2023) suggest that an institutional approach is well-suited for studying RECs, due to the complex negotiations that involve a diverse array of participants and stakeholders.

¹ “Participatory instruments (...) able to provide adequate modes of regulation. A framework of agreements, with the incentive forms linked to it, presupposes a state in retreat from its traditional functions, renouncing its power of constraint and becoming involved in modes of ostensibly contractual exchange, mobilizing and enrolling resources and actors” (Le Galès, 2010, p.11).

The implementation of RECs represents a key opportunity for advancing a just and inclusive local energy transition. As shown in various case studies presented in literature, RECs foster social innovation by enabling citizens, civil society organisations, local authorities, and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) to become active participants in the energy system. This shift transforms them from passive consumers into prosumers who both produce and consume energy (Hanke et al, 2021).

Focusing on how actors involved in governance processes operate (Le Galès, 2010, p. 1), citizens and civil society organisations can influence the energy governance structures and contribute to bottom-up energy transition by becoming energy prosumers within a REC. Their involvement can occur in collaboration with municipalities and SMEs, regardless of which stakeholder leads the REC initiative.

However, the development of decentralised and more democratic energy supply models, predicated on RECs and energy efficiency cannot be left solely to private initiatives. This effort requires careful integration within existing energy and climate planning policies. This includes the incorporation of sustainable energy objectives into urban and regional plans and the adoption of broader integrated energy planning approaches (De Pascali & Bagaini, 2018; Asarpota & Nadin, 2020).

RECs thus serve as local transition initiatives that promote decentralised, participatory and democratic energy systems. These initiatives generate social, economic and technological returns within their territories (Bolognesi & Magnaghi, 2020).

Moreover, RECs can be assessed through their alignment with local energy potential and their ability to foster self-organised energy systems at the territorial level, which is increasingly central to political decision-making.

As the energy transition advances, the energy sector evolves from a centralised national industry into a key area of public policy with a pronounced territorial dimension. This transformation involves both urban and rural areas and reflects the shift towards diversified, multi-scale energy production and distribution systems (Araújo, 2014).

Research gaps, research questions, and objectives

To date, the analysis of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) supply, as well as RECs configurations, has been mostly focused on their social, economic, and environmental benefits (e.g. Kiamba et al, 2022; Algarni et al, 2023, among others) or organisational models (De Vidovich et al, 2023), being their spatial governance and planning dimension a trivial issue. In particular, at the local level, the mismatch between energy planning and spatial planning is critical, and the potential of shaping spatial and urban forms in the interests of energy efficiency is often overlooked (Roger-Lacan, 2019; Asarpota & Nadin, 2020). Nowak et al (2022) collected several European case studies to highlight how the interaction between

spatial governance and planning and renewables is noticeable, and how legal barriers limit the establishment of distributed energy configurations more than technological ones.

Therefore, the frequent lack of a spatial dimension and adequate articulation between different institutional levels in the definition and implementation of energy and climate strategies is the main research gap addressed by this paper. The potential of having an integrated energy, climate, and spatial planning approach is often underestimated, despite spatial planning being the crucial element for sustainable and resilient local development (IN-PLAN, 2023)². Local development plans frequently exhibit an absence of integration with climate and energy strategies and may also limit the implementation of renewable energy investments. Arguably, this is attributable to the failure of local development plans to provide adequate technical regulations, financial incentives, fiscal conditions and the promotion of public-private partnerships to define, finance and implement projects (Solarek & Kubasińska, 2022).

All that being said, the main research question of the paper is “How do local and regional governance and planning frameworks influence the development and implementation of RECs as instruments of a just local energy transition in different European institutional contexts?”

In order to answer this question, the paper aims to:

- Identify the main institutional, legal, and regulatory frameworks suitable for the establishment and functioning of RECs at the local and regional levels, and the regulatory barriers affecting the RECs.
- Examine the relationship between the local and regional levels and the relationships between these levels and the actors in the implementation of the RECs.
- Examine how spatial and energy planning frameworks interact and influence the development of RECs.
- Explore the role of public authorities in facilitating, promoting, or potentially constraining REC initiatives through policy instruments, governance practices, and support mechanisms.
- Analyse how different governance structures and institutional arrangements affect stakeholder engagement in RECs.

To this purpose, three distinct European regional contexts are examined: the Piedmont Region in Italy, the Autonomous Community of Andalusia in Spain, and the Canton of Geneva in Switzerland. These contexts empirically illustrate a range of institutional settings and experiences representing meaningful practices and show to what extent activation policy is defined at the national and regional levels, while it is implemented at the municipal level, where different practices and social impacts can be observed.

² <https://fedarene.org/project/in-plan/>

Methodology and conceptual framework

This paper investigates the activation processes of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) through a comparative analysis of three regional case studies: Piedmont (Italy), Andalusia (Spain), and Geneva (Switzerland). These regions were selected to represent varying degrees of regional autonomy and to reflect different legal, regulatory, and institutional frameworks within the broader European context.

The EU introduced RECs in the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package in 2019. The Internal Energy Market Directive (IEMD) introduced the concept of Citizens' Energy Communities (CECs), and the recast of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) introduced the so-called RECs. Based on EU Directives, each member State is supposed to approve and implement its respective legal and regulatory framework.

Although Switzerland is not an EU Member State, its national energy legislation aligns with similar principles. The Federal Law on secure electricity provision based on renewable energy provisions, especially from PV, approved in 2024, creates favourable conditions to accelerate the national renewable energy development, also in terms of incentives, and in so doing, stabilising the solar energy sector. In Switzerland, Local Energy Communities (LECs) and Virtual Self-consumption Groups (VSCs) enable the local trade of solar energy using the connection line and the public electricity grid, thus favouring the optimisation of production, storage and consumption at a decentralised level.

Selection of case studies

The selected case studies highlight a variety of institutional settings and levels of articulation between national, regional, and local authorities. The regions fall under the NUTS2 (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics, level 2) classification provided by Eurostat³.

The three case studies are presented in *Case studies* section, and show different nuances of regional autonomy. Italy has limited regional autonomy, Spain has a high regional autonomy, and the federal system of Switzerland offers to the Cantons a wide autonomy and strong implementation capacity in a number of policy sectors.

The selection of these case studies - whose data were mainly collected on the occasion of an INTERREG EUROPE project proposal by the authors of the present paper - offers an insight into the variable geometry of regional conditions for the development of place-based RECs' activation initiatives, which can leverage endogenous innovations, both in terms of needs and solutions. In particular, these cases represent a variety of institutional settings and forms of articulation between national, regional and local levels.

The Italian case represents the joint or individual municipal efforts towards leading the activation of RECs throughout the respective local communities and the articulation between

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts>

top-down (municipalities and ESCOs) and bottom-up (citizens' initiatives) approaches. The Spanish case represents the social engagement deserving vulnerable contexts. The Swiss case represents the REC's establishment as a driver of redevelopment projects to implement energy transition by means of public-private partnerships.

Methodological approach

This study adopts a comparative policy analysis approach, conceptualising RECs as instruments of climate and energy policy. It employs qualitative methods to examine the interplay between policy frameworks and local activation processes. Firstly, the paper designs a comparative multilevel governance framework of the three cases referring to the REC establishment process (*The multilevel framework related to RECs in three European Regions*). Subsequently, the paper critically revises the three cases to understand which are the relationships between the local, regional and national levels with respect to the successful establishment of RECs (*The interplay of local, regional and national levels in the establishment of RECs in the three case studies*) and finally, it discusses *The multilevel framework*, and *The RECs' activation*. The paper devotes particular attention to the eventual integration of energy/climate policies and urban planning.

Data were collected from official sources, i.e. policy documents, planning tools, and institutional websites. Semi-structured interviews were carried out in 2023 and 2024 with RECs' relevant stakeholders, including civil servants and politicians from the regional, provincial and municipal levels of government, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) committed to climate change mitigation and ecological transition, and academic experts.

For each case study involved at least five interviews were conducted, each lasting at least one hour, utilising a structured questionnaire. The content of these interviews encompassed the following areas: (1) the genesis and evolution of RECs, (2) obstacles or barriers encountered during the establishment process, (3) the adequacy of legal arrangements, (4) the role of local authorities and legal and regulatory provisions in facilitating the effective establishment of the REC, (5) the relationships between the local, regional and national levels, and in the particular the role played by the regional level, (6) social issues related to stakeholders' engagement.

For the Italian case, three municipal political representatives and two municipal public servants were interviewed. The Sustainable Energy Development Office of the Piedmont Region was interviewed on three occasions, along with the policy design process.

In the Spanish case, the Andalusian Energy Agency and the Granada Energy Agency were interviewed. Two different representatives from Torreblanca Illumina REC were interviewed as well as one from the *Rio Monachil REC*.

The Swiss case was presented in Task 63 - Solar Neighbourhood Planning (International Energy Agency) among other case studies⁴. Two representatives from the Foundation for Industrial Areas of Geneva (FTI) and from the Energy Entity of Geneva (SIG) were interviewed, respectively, in order to discuss with both a technician and an institutional representative for each entity. Finally, a representative from the cantonal energy department was also interviewed concerning the institutional and legal aspects of REC.

With reference to *The interplay of local, regional and national levels in the establishment of RECs in the three case studies*, the following figure summarises the common conceptual framework against which the case studies are analysed and compared. It is developed considering a multi-level framework articulating the national, regional and local levels. Each institutional level can facilitate and frame the initiation of RECs through regulations, subsidies, plans and other tools. The REC aggregation is made up of several stakeholders, distinguishing those who initiate (invest in), manage or simply participate to the REC.

Figure 1 – Common conceptual framework for the analysis of the case studies.

Case studies

Piedmont Region, Italy

In compliance with the EU Directives 2018/2001 and 2019/944 regarding the promotion of RES and common rules for the internal electricity market, respectively, Italy has approved two Legislative Decrees, LD 199/2021 and LD 210/2021, to complete the national regulatory framework concerning energy self-consumption and energy communities. According to LD 199/2021, electricity can be shared between users within the same market area (of which Italy has six), while access to incentives for sharing electricity from renewable sources are exclusively reserved for users connected to the same primary substation and are limited to the share derived from new plants with a nominal power rating of less than 1 MW. To fully apply

⁴ <https://task63.iea-shc.org/case-studies>
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Ej91oe6mSKbhon2oKpL_Ev6dDzf4uK1j/view

the LD 199/2021, the Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment (*Autorità di Regolazione per l'Energia e l'Ambiente, ARERA*) issued a series of resolutions and introduced a virtual regulatory model for widespread self-consumption. To implement this policy, the only recently approved Ministerial Decree MD 414/2024 introduces two main support measures: (i) non-repayable grants covering up to 40% of eligible costs, financed by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), specifically addressed to municipalities with populations under 5,000 residents, and intended to support the development of 2 GW of total renewable capacity; and (ii) an incentive tariff applied to renewable energy produced and shared across the national territory. These two measures can be combined, and the incentive tariffs will be available until either a national capacity of 5 GW is reached or until 31 December 2027, whichever is sooner. Regarding installation limits, the decree specifies that the maximum nominal capacity of an individual plant or an upgrade intervention cannot exceed 1 MW. The financial support offered by Ministerial Decree 414 should encourage small local governments to activate RECs located within their respective territories.

Regarding the features of RECs, LD 199/2021 (art 2 and art 31) explains that a REC is an autonomous, non-profit legal entity (e.g. an association, cooperative, or consortium) based on open, voluntary participation from companies, individuals, municipal authorities, and religious authorities, as well as organisations from the third sector and other local authorities. However, for companies, participation in a REC cannot constitute their primary economic activity. Both public and private members can be prosumers or consumers to reap economic benefits.

Turning to the regional legislative and regulatory framework, Piedmont was the first Region in Italy to approve a regional law on RECs, making Piedmont a pioneer in REC legislation. The Regional Law (LR 03/08/2018, n. 12) on the Promotion of the Establishment of Energy Communities attributes a territorial dimension to energy communities. Municipalities act as promoters, based on a memorandum of understanding and supervise the development of activities and the relationships among community members. After their constitution, RECs were supposed to set up an energy balance and a strategic document regarding energy saving and efficiency. Furthermore, RECs were expected to produce energy for self-consumption equalling at least 70 % of the total. The Piedmont Region also approved DGR n. 18-8520 8/03/2019, which specified the minimum requirements for a REC. However, the specific modalities proposed by the law have remained on the paper, and the REC establishment has been a bottom-up process led by municipalities or local stakeholders.

Beyond that law, the Piedmont Region currently prospects a regional role of territorial coordination, which consists of soft monitoring of REC initiatives, creating a REC regional network, raising awareness and building capacity, and facilitating relationships with

institutional entities, such as ARERA⁵, GSE⁶, RSE⁷, MISE⁸, and energy distributors, and providing support to RECs in their applications for EU funds.

Moving now from the regional to the municipal level, in Piedmont, two-thirds of the municipalities have fewer than 5,000 inhabitants and are therefore potential NRRP beneficiaries. Among them, Scalenghe is a small municipality belonging to the Metropolitan City of Turin. In 2019, Scalenghe, together with other municipalities in the Pinerolese area, signed a memorandum of understanding called the 'Oil Free Zone'. Based on this agreement, in 2021 the temporary association of municipalities known as the 'Pinerolese Renewable Energy Community' (ATS)⁹ was established, including 41 municipalities, most of which have fewer than 5,000 inhabitants. However, the ATS has not progressed to become an operational REC and, according to the interviewees, this is due to the uncertain Italian REC regulation, only recently clarified by the aforementioned MD 414/2024.

Scalenghe is leading the ATS, with the municipality's vice mayor serving as ATS president. The municipalities involved are committed to the local energy transition. Supported by a private fund called 'Next Generation You', issued by Compagnia di San Paolo (an Italian bank foundation), in 2021-22, they developed the feasibility studies for setting a REC with the technical support of the Politecnico di Torino. Rather than using a subdivision by primary substation, these preliminary activities were developed by grouping the ATS municipalities in seven clusters, which, as observed by interviewees, makes the REC's activation even less viable.

It is worth mentioning that the aforementioned seven clusters developed the contents of the ATS Pinerolese's joint Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP), which is aimed at addressing climate change mitigation and adaptation collectively. However, due to legal constraints, each municipality was required to approve its own SECAP separately. Among other actions, the joint SECAP includes the organisation of joint energy management, and the activation of RECs is one of the main pillars for increasing local renewable energy production. Nevertheless, the SECAP is not directly connected to the respective municipal master plan, as well as the land use assignments are inconsistent with the actions proposed by the SECAP. Consequently, the municipalities of the ATS Pinerolese have not yet integrated spatial planning and energy planning. Each municipality is implementing these plans in isolation.

Due to the impasse in activating the Pinerolese REC, the municipality of Cantalupa decided to create its own REC by including the neighbouring municipalities of Roletto and Frossasco, grouped under the same primary substation. Among the REC's founders are some local SMEs, the parish, and a hotel. The municipalities are not included for legal reasons. Specifically, the Cantalupa-led REC is a non-recognized association, a model acknowledged by

⁵ Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente

⁶ Gestore dei servizi energetici

⁷ Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico

⁸ Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico

⁹ ATS, Associazione Temporanea di Scopo <https://www.atspinerolese.it/>

the Italian legislation that offers no guarantees to the municipalities. As the interviewees mentioned, municipalities tend to prefer legal forms such as cooperatives or consortia, as these offer greater managerial autonomy than associations and reduce the risk of direct oversight by the Court of Auditors. In these structures, the municipality can participate as a member and delegate operational management to third parties, thereby limiting municipal administrative and financial exposure. The decision to opt out of the legal structure of an association for RECs is frequently motivated by the objective of minimising administrative responsibility and the risk of rigorous oversight by the Court of Auditors. This tendency favours legal solutions that offer enhanced greater flexibility and reduced personal risks for municipal administrators.

Other municipalities located in the Pinerolese area are implementing different REC models, and they are about to establish their RECs under the legal configuration of a 'participatory foundation', for instance, the municipality of Villafranca. These local authorities opted for being supported by an Energy Service Company (ESCO) which directly invests in the photovoltaic (PV) installations on municipal roofs and pays the municipality for the surface rights (i.e. 10 euros per kW installed). The ESCO is responsible for the REC's long-term management (approximately 20 years) and will sell the energy to the citizens. This integrated model enables municipalities to alleviate the financial obligations associated with establishing a REC, while concurrently diminishing the benefits, particularly the social ones.

In the same area, out of the ATS Pinerolese, another interesting REC configuration was settled in the municipality of Sangano, in December 2023. The REC initiative was led by private users (mainly SMEs) and called Sangano Common Energy (*Sangano Energia Comune*), It operates within the regional legal framework of the community cooperative (Regional Law 28 May 2021, n. 13)¹⁰. This social innovation model is addressed to citizen participation mainly in small centres, in the mountain, marginal, and inner areas, with difficult access and connection to infrastructure and service networks. For these areas, where even essential services are at risk, citizens can play an effective role in providing answers to common needs, creating job opportunities for young people and exploiting local development potential. This model was selected because it is feasible and allows the participation of the municipality at a later stage.

The municipality of Sangano played a crucial role in the initial phase of the REC's activation by organizing several meetings with citizens, for example, a REC festival in June 2023. It consisted of three full days of debates and discussions (by covering technical, legal, and social issues), which involved experts from academia, industry, and consultancy experts in the field of energy. Furthermore, one of the interviewees recognised the key role of the Compagnia di San Paolo Foundation in supporting the municipality of Sangano through the

¹⁰ <https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/temi/istruzione-formazione-lavoro/lavoro/sostegno-allimprenditorialita-cooperazione/cooperative-comunita>

“Sinergie” fund, which was used for preliminary studies and mapping stakeholders, as well as providing institutional support.

Local private players in Sangano have taken a proactive attitude, competing with national and local ESCOs, which have recently demonstrated a keen interest in supporting the activation of RECs by proposing Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs), which enable users to avoid initial investment. In contrast, the municipality has decided to fulfil its role as aggregator by networking and planning to join the REC at a later stage, transferring existing municipal PV installations to the REC in the process. This private, bottom-up initiative has simplified the process of setting up a REC which is already operational. The current Italian REC framework enables public authorities to participate in a REC; however, until now, local public action has been confined to the promotion of the REC’s principles and the support of participatory activities to facilitate their bottom-up initiatives. According to the Vice Major of Sangano, the municipality’s participatory and networking approach, which prioritised REC activation in the political mandate, has enabled the activation of further municipal programmes and projects in collaboration with surrounding municipalities. For example, the municipality participated in drafting the Urban Area Strategy (*SUA, Strategia Urbana d’Area*), which includes energy-related topics.

Moreover, the cooperative community model of Sangano’s REC is being evaluated by the ATS Pinerolese, alongside other models. The involved municipalities are torn between embracing the integrated ESCO-led initiative, which has fewer administrative burdens but fewer benefits, and choosing Sangano’s bottom-up solution, which has more benefits but more administrative burdens.

Among the most common issues which limit the RECs’ activation, the unclear national and regional legislation is mentioned by the municipal representatives interviewed, as well as the existence of many institutional actors, including the Ministry of Environmental and Energy Security (*Ministero dell’Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica*), GSE, ARERA, and the regional government, which overlap in the definition of clear rules and responsibilities. Furthermore, municipal policymakers are afraid of the control of the Court of Auditors, which can restrict the participation of public entities in RECs. Economic constraints are also among the current limitations. The administrative management of RECs is very expensive regardless of their legal status, and the national incentives do not directly cover these costs. The GSE, managing the national register of RECs, lasts three months to fulfil this task. In the meantime, future REC members need to apply for the NRRP funding, which covers 40% of costs in municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants. According to the interviewees, this mechanism is a vicious cycle, because the members of a REC cannot apply for national incentives without already having installed PV panels, but the aspiring prosumers cannot install PV panels without the GSE national registration.

Almost all of the interviewees acknowledged that a factor somehow influencing also the RECs' activation is the regional financial support from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) dedicated to the municipal energy transition. Although no specific regional funds on the RECs activation have been allocated, the ERDF fund has mostly been addressed to public buildings' energy retrofitting. These funds have enabled the most advanced municipalities for long-term planning of their energy transition, including RECs' activation. On the contrary, legal, technical, and institutional support has primarily been provided by such private funding institutions as the Compagnia di San Paolo Foundation.

Moreover, all of the analysed local case studies from the Piedmont Region reveal a discrepancy between climate and energy policies (primarily the SECAPs) and spatial planning. In fact, in the municipalities belonging to the ATS Pinerolese (including Scalenghe), municipal master plans are not connected to the approved SECAPs. In Sangano, no SECAP has yet been approved, and the path towards its definition has only recently been undertaken. According to all the interviewees, the regional government has not understood the need to foster spatial and energy planning jointly to tackle climate change challenges and to go towards a fair energy transition for all.

Autonomous Community of Andalusia, Spain

Spain is divided into Autonomous Communities (Regions), Provinces and Municipalities. At the national level, the Spanish Royal Decree-Law 23/2020 includes various measures for economic recovery, encompassing the energy sector, and amends several articles of Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector. This provision defines RECs as legal entities based on open and voluntary participation. They must be autonomous and effectively controlled by partners or members who are located in the surroundings of renewable energy installations owned and developed by such legal entities. Partners or members can be physical persons, SMEs or local authorities, including municipalities, whose primary purpose is to provide environmental, economic or social benefits to their partners or members, or to the local areas where they operate, rather than financial gain¹¹. The Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan 2021-2030 (INECP) includes 'energy communities' among the measures envisaged to ensure the energy transition (Revuelta Pérez, 2022). The most common REC arrangement is composed of one or more collective self-consumption aggregations, which can currently be implemented within a limited radius from the installation site (Galera Rodrigo, 2023). In this solution, each REC can encompass several aggregations within the same legal entity. Regarding incentives, the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge has implemented the

¹¹<https://www.idae.es/ayudas-y-financiacion/comunidades-energeticas>

Incentive Programme for Individual Pilot Projects of Energy Communities (*CE IMPLEMENTA*)¹², under the framework of the NRRP, funded by the NextGenerationEU¹³.

The latter identifies RECs as key players in the energy transition, providing these entities with the financial capacity necessary to develop the construction and commissioning activities for facilities promoting social participation in the energy sector. Aid will be granted in the form of a non-refundable subsidy, which beneficiaries will receive once the project execution and investment have been verified. *CE IMPLEMENTA* is managed by the Spanish Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (*Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía, IDAE*), which also manages *CE OFICINAS*. This programme provides funding for Community Transformation Offices to promote and activate RECs. Moreover, Spain has a National Strategy Against Energy Poverty 2019-2024¹⁴. Between 3.5 and 8.1 million people are affected by energy poverty, according to different calculation methods.

Moving from the national to the regional levels, still referring to the problem of energy poverty, it must be observed that the “social bonus”, i.e. the public aid addressed to families to pay energy bills, is an insufficient mechanism in some regions. Andalusia is one of these regions. The Andalusian regional government has approved the first Comprehensive Strategic Plan for the Elderly in Andalusia 2020-2023,¹⁵ financed by ERDF funds and the European Interreg Europe program. This plan requires a prior diagnosis of energy poverty in the elderly group, carried out by the Andalusian Energy Agency¹⁶, which prioritises the development and promotion of RECs, as stated in the Andalusian Energy Strategy 2030 approved by the Governing Council on 7 June 2022. The Agency provides technical advice to Andalusian energy communities and local entities that are trying to set up REC projects. Within the Andalusian Self-consumption Board, the Agency participates in the Local Energy Communities Working Group, which focuses on RECs’ promotion and collective self-consumption.

The Region of Andalusia is a partner in the *Powerty* Interreg Europe project,¹⁷ which is aimed at increasing the use of renewable energies in vulnerable social groups. Throughout its participation in the *Powerty* project, the Region of Andalusia is refining an existing policy instrument¹⁸ that could be used to promote the RECs’ establishment and development in vulnerable contexts where families may suffer from energy poverty.

Moving from the regional to the local level, this is the case of the Energy and Educational *Torreblanca* Community,¹⁹ which was originally established to combat energy poverty

¹² <https://sede.idae.gob.es/lang/modulo/?refbol=tramites-servicios&refsec=comunidades-energeticas&idarticulo=146972>

¹³ <https://www.idae.es/ayudas-y-financiacion/comunidades-energeticas/programa-de-incentivos-proyectos-piloto-singulares-de>

¹⁴ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/ministerio/planes-estrategias/estrategia-pobreza-energetica.html>

¹⁵ <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/transparencia/planificacion-evaluacion-estadistica/planes/detalle/208782.html>

¹⁶ <https://www.agenciaandaluzadelaenergia.es/es>

¹⁷ <https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/powerty/>

¹⁸ ERDF 2014-2020. Objective T.O.4. Priority Line 4.c.: Support the energy efficiency, smart energy management and renewable energy use in public infrastructure, including in public buildings, and the housing sector.

¹⁹ <http://www.torreblancaalumina.com/>

(Bouzarovski, 2014; Parreño-Rodríguez et al, 2023)²⁰. Torreblanca Ilumina is located in the Barrio Torreblanca in the municipal area of Seville and is supported by the Region of Andalusia within the aforementioned *Powerty* project. These European funds were channelled through a collaboration agreement signed at the beginning of 2022 between the Agency and the *Torreblanca Ilumina* Association, which was set up to create an energy and learning community in the Torreblanca neighbourhood of Seville. This agreement made it possible to finance a study of the various key aspects necessary to materialise and execute this pilot action. This included the legal assistance required to overcome all the legal challenges associated with the implementation of this type of collective self-consumption initiative.

In Barrio Torreblanca, a vulnerable²¹ neighbourhood with more than 18.000 inhabitants, the roofs of two municipal infant and primary schools were covered with PV panels by the municipality. Starting from scratch, the Organising Committee of Torreblanca Ilumina has been formed through an incremental process involving the educational communities of the two schools, the Civic Centre Juan Antonio González Caraballo, the Centre of Community Social Services, the Local Group of Som Energía Energy Cooperative, the research group ADICI²² of the University of Seville, and the Ecosocial Workshop.

In February 2021, the non-profit association Torreblanca Ilumina was created (see Agencia Andaluza de la Energía, 2023). It encompasses the energy self-consumption groups, with a total capacity of 15 kW, one for each school. Each group is composed of one school and a group of local families in partial energy poverty (11-13 families). This REC also manages – but does not own – a third PV installation, equivalent to 50 kW, owned by one of its members: the Seville Autism Association²³. The initiative received financial support from the municipality, the Andalusian Energy Agency and the *Som Energia* Energy Cooperative. As interviewees pointed out, the electricity distributor obstructed the REC's connection to the grid due to unclear regulations, decelerating the project implementation. The role of the municipality has also proven to be critical because the Municipality of Seville was not prepared to sign an agreement for such an initiative, and the granting of public surfaces over the school roof took a long time.

Besides, Torreblanca is currently included in the Neighbourhood Plan and was designated a Disadvantaged Area by the Andalusian Regional Government. In Andalusia, the participation of civil society organisations in REC development is detectable not only in the Torreblanca experience. In fact, the Region finances the School of Social Economy²⁴ in Seville, which offers a traineeship programme for REC creation based on the social economy

²⁰ The factors that affect energy poverty levels are household income, price of energy and degree of energy efficiency achieved in households among others. No just one indicator measures energy poverty, which not only impacts the functionality of homes but also it affects several other aspects, including health and social stigma. Solidarity and participation are levers that must be integrated, along with initiatives to improve the quality of life for urban dwellers living in energy poverty (Parreño-Rodríguez et al, 2023).

²¹ The National Statistics Institute's Urban Indicators 2021 rank it as the fourth most disadvantaged area in the country, with one of the lowest average annual net incomes per inhabitant in Spain.

²² Aula digital de la ciudad

²³ <https://www.autismosevilla.org/>

²⁴ <https://escueladeeconomiasocial.es/>

principles. Despite such a remarkable institution, there is still a lack of an adequate regional ecosystem of SMEs, cooperatives and third-sector entities committed to activating and developing RECs, is missing. Similarly, entrepreneurial capacity in the renewable energy sector is not widespread.

Andalusia presents further REC experiences spread across the regional territory. Among the others, in the Province of Granada, composed of the Granada metropolitan area (35 municipalities), and a rural area (174 municipalities, of which 135 have fewer than 5,000 inhabitants and only eight have more than 20,000), at least seven RECs have been activated by 2024. In 2019, the Granada Provincial Council launched a Climate Change Adaptation Plan in 2019 to better assess impacts and possible solutions, as well as to implement the 'Local Programme for the Just Energy Transition' that foresees a Community Transformation Office dedicated to the promotion of RECs in 2024-25. These offices are designed to provide information, advice and support to individuals, SMEs and local authorities in setting up and managing energy communities.

The Granada Energy Agency provides municipalities with free technical support for energy transition and SECAP preparation and has participated in the EU-funded Shared Green Deal project²⁵. While half of the municipalities have approved a SECAP primarily to secure EU funding, they have also adopted the Climate Change Municipal Plan, which is mandatory under regional law. Consequently, the Government of Andalusia finances the preparation of the Municipal Climate Change Plan (Plan Municipal contra el Cambio Climático, PMCC) for all the municipalities with fewer than 50,000 inhabitants.

In Granada province, the *Río Monachil* Energy Community²⁶ was created in 2020, based on a cooperation agreement with the Municipality of Monachil. This agreement permits the use of the Miraflores Sporting Centre roof to install a 10kW plant. This installation provides energy for 15 residential buildings, including the municipal building in which it is located. Around 5% of the energy produced will be made available to families in energy poverty at a nominal price. The activation procedures are being implemented, and the REC currently includes 56 families and two SMEs. Finally, based on *Project POCITYF*²⁷ regarding the development of REC in protected heritage areas, in the historical Granada the *Barrio de l'Alambra Energy Community* was established in May 2023, in order to settle an installation outside the protected area and to connect it to families located inside the area.

To sum up, the Spanish national government recognises the role of RECs by means of the INECP, in line with the NextGenerationEU fund, and provides incentives for them through the *CE IMPLEMENTA* programme. Furthermore, a national strategy has been developed to combat energy poverty, recognising the relevance of the problem. In this regard, the

²⁵ <https://sharedgreendeal.eu/hubs/granada-community-visions-community-energy>

²⁶ <https://cesocial.es/>
<https://cermonachil.org/>

²⁷ <https://pocityf.eu/>

Andalusian regional level engages in dialogue with the national level and has developed a strategy for the elderly, who are among those most often affected by energy poverty. This strategy is implemented by the Andalusian Energy Agency, which operates within the regional energy strategy (Andalusian Energy Strategy 2030). The regional level, which concentrates its efforts on the agency and dialogues with the local level through its active participation in the *Powerty* Interreg Europe project. The latter contributed to the start-up process of Torreblanca Illumina; a REC created with the intention of reducing energy poverty in an extremely vulnerable neighbourhood. In fact, the REC's establishment is supported by the agency, and the municipality merely grants use of the areas above the schools. Furthermore, the recognition of Torreblanca as a disadvantaged area is a regional responsibility.

The Region should coordinate initiatives within its regional territory, as well as ensure cooperation between the regional and the national levels, even in collaboration with the other Spanish Regions.

Regional law 8/2018²⁸, regarding measures against climate change and for the transition to a new energy model in Andalusia, obliges municipalities to approve climate change plans to replace fossil fuels for municipal consumption with locally produced renewable energies and building energy retrofitting, art. 15. Although the plan does not mention energy communities, it allows for the adoption of regulatory measures that favour energy self-consumption of renewable energy and the participation of local actors in the production and distribution of renewable energy, art. 34 (Revuelta Pérez, 2022).

Therefore, in Andalusia, municipalities have to comply with the regional government's mandate to prepare municipal climate change plans, as well as with the SECAP approval, which is one of the legal conditions for receiving European grants. This means that each municipality has two parallel and distinguished tools for the same topics: one to comply with the national planning framework, and another to comply with the European policies. This creates an unjustified and misleading duplication. However, the Andalusian regional government's planning instrument takes precedence over the SECAP in technical terms, despite European funds being collected within the SECAP framework. This creates a discrepancy between regional regulation and project implementation.

Canton of Geneva, Switzerland

Switzerland is a Confederation divided into Cantons and Communes. The Federal Energy Strategy 2050²⁹, endorsed in a referendum in 2018, serves as the primary roadmap for the national energy transition, encompassing the phasing-out of nuclear power, the expansion of RES and RECs, and improvements in building efficiency.

²⁸ <https://www.boe.es/eli/es-an/l/2018/10/08/8>

²⁹ <https://www.bfe.admin.ch/bfe/en/home/policy/energy-strategy-2050.html/>

At the federal level, the Swiss Federal Energy Law (2016)³⁰ allows and promotes the self-consumption of locally produced electricity, particularly from solar energy, enabling the sale of surplus energy to the national grid (art. 16), and the establishment of RECs, whether at the level of a single building, plot, or neighbourhood (art. 17). Once they have been grouped, end consumers have a single metering point with the grid operator. Therefore, they must be treated as a single end-user (art. 18) with a single billing connection to the main grid, in order to sell the locally produced surplus energy or purchase electricity not supplied by the local energy installation. A prerequisite for REC is that the electricity generated on-site can be consumed directly via a dedicated microgrid, bypassing without using the distribution grid. In other words, solar PV production can be shared among multi-family residences or clusters of neighbouring buildings. Such RECs can be managed either by the owners of the surfaces or by third-party entities such as energy suppliers. The microgrid is connected to the main grid to sell the surplus of solar energy production or, conversely, to buy electricity from the grid when the solar production is insufficient.

Until recently, buildings connected to a solar microgrid had to be adjacent to each other. However, this obstacle was overcome following the referendum on 9 June 2024, which resulted in the passing of the new "Federal Act on the Security of Electricity Supply from Renewable Energy Sources"³¹. This new law (art. 17) introduces the concept of shared solar energy production between distant and non-contiguous buildings through the establishment of Local Electricity Communities. End consumers, renewable electricity producers, and storage operators can form groups that independently manage their electricity supply throughout the distribution network, within a single municipality.

Energy Cooperatives can also manage remote solar communities where individuals self-organise to finance local projects, such as solar installations, in the form of capital shares. A notable example in the region of Nyon (Canton de Vaud, 2023) is Optima Solar La Côte³². Citizens, public authorities, companies, associations, and other organisations can purchase a share in the cooperative's capital (with an initial nominal value of 1,000 Swiss francs). Each person thus becomes a co-producer of solar-generated electricity. All the shares are used to finance the solar power plants. The cooperative does not take out bank loans. From the third year after installation, the annual remuneration of each share is determined based on the previous year's financial results (up to a maximum of 2%). Any additional profits are reinvested in new installations. The value of the shares is guaranteed for 25 years. Each share can be transferred, resold or redeemed. The cooperative's activities promote the local production of renewable, ecological and traceable electricity. To date, 20 solar communities

³⁰ Loi sur l'énergie (LEne) du 30 septembre 2016 <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2017/762/fr>

Ordonnance sur l'énergie (OEne) du 1er novembre 2017 <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2017/763/fr>

³¹ <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/fga/2023/2301/fr>

³² <https://optimasolar-lacote.ch/>

utilising this model have been initiated in Switzerland, often based on solar installations on school roofs.

At the regional level, each Canton maintains its own energy legislation, which is expected to align with federal guidelines and contribute to the implementation of the federal Energy Strategy 2050. The Energy Act of Geneva is one of the most ambitious in Switzerland. Based on the Energy Master Plan 2020-2030, it is implemented through the Cantonal Energy Act and ordinances. It promotes, among other actions, a significant increase in building renovations, the development of district heating and cooling networks based on Lake Geneva and geothermal energy, and the recovery of heat from wastewater treatment plants. It also aims to massively increase solar energy production, from 60 MW in 2020 to over 300 MW by 2030 (120 MW by 2024). Accordingly, the Energy Act requires the installation of PV solar panels in all new and renovated buildings, with a minimum capacity of 10 W/m² of floor area. It also explicitly prohibits the use of fossil fuels in new buildings and boiler replacements, except in district heating networks that may contain a partial fossil fuel component.

At the local level, municipalities play a pivotal role in implementing federal and cantonal regulations. Several cities (482 by May 2025) have been awarded the "*Cité de l'énergie*" label (Energy European Award). This is the case of many small- and medium-sized municipalities. Satigny (3,300 inhabitants) located in the Canton of Geneva, is one such municipality. It was first certified as a "*Cité de l'énergie*" in 2011. Satigny is a mainly rural municipality comprising a village centre and three industrial sites, including the Bois-de-Bay Industrial Zone (ZIBAY)³³, which will be presented afterwards. In Geneva's communes, a territorial energy policy is implemented through communal energy master plans. Satigny's municipal energy master plan (Desthieux et al, 2018), drawn up in 2018, aims to define the levers of action and strategies to reduce the territory's energy consumption and induced GHGs; increase the share of local RES in the energy supply; identify opportunities for developing energy infrastructure and facilitate coordination between the various players in the energy sector. The valorisation of the potential of such industrial sites as ZIBAY is therefore strategic for the municipal energy policy.

The ZIBAY is one of the industrial areas in the canton of Geneva, located in the municipality of Satigny. ZIBAY covers an area of 79 ha and brings together up to 200 companies (approximately 1,800 jobs) mainly in the construction, automotive mechanics, recycling, and logistics sectors. In ZIBAY, the FTI grants building rights to companies wishing to set up in the area. The FTI is a public company owned by the Canton of Geneva and is responsible for developing the industrial estate and promoting business development in the Canton of Geneva.

³³ This case study was presented in Task 63 - Solar Neighbourhood Planning (International Energy Agency) among other case studies worldwide (<https://task63.iea-shc.org/case-studies>), and its content has been updated for the present paper.

As a public company owned by the Canton of Geneva, FTI is committed to supporting the energy transition of industries that have building rights on their land. A solar microgrid project was implemented by a consortium made up of FTI and SIG. In addition, SIG has a service contract for the technical installation, maintenance and operation of the microgrid. A consortium has been established, associating the six industrial partners, has been established to consolidate the self-consumption of solar energy under the Federal Energy Act. Specific regulations have been drawn up to govern the contractual aspects between the partners. The REC is represented by the FTI/SIG consortium. In accordance with the Energy Act, electricity price for all companies connected to the microgrid is more favourable than the market price, with tariffs adapted to the type of consumer.

In 2014, FTI launched the Bois-de-Bay EcoPark initiative to identify and promote synergies between industrial companies and the sustainable development of their economic activities, with a particular focus on energy efficiency and low carbon impact. Consultations with local companies and partners confirmed the need for local energy planning. This culminated in the 2017 project for a major solar installation (1.38 MWp) on one of the new buildings, implemented by a consortium associating FTI and SIG. The solar installation came into service in August 2021, intending to create a micro-grid by 2026, pooling the solar energy produced by the new buildings on neighbouring plots, to form thus a REC.

These buildings are essentially warehouses with limited energy demand, except for the green waste methanisation plant (biogas), which requires a very large amount of electricity (30-40% of REC's total demand) for the process³⁴. Ultimately, the project will have a total solar capacity of 3 MWp (1.6 MWp by 2024) and a self-consumption rate of 60% through the microgrid (12% in 2024).

This considerable self-consumption rate will be achieved by installing a storage plant for the truck charging stations, or by changing the orientation of the solar panel domes (east-west or south-north).

This development was led by FTI, which owns the industrial land and invested in a project with no minimum profitability requirement, with financial risks that a private investor could not take on. Initially, the investment decision was based on a single guaranteed customer: the hall in which the main solar installation is located has a maximum self-consumption potential of only 10%. However, FTI, as the landowner, can require other companies to connect to the microgrid as part of the land rights, which is an important legal lever. Ultimately, the risk-taking paid off: other large consumers joined the project, including the biogas plant and the road company with its fleet of electric trucks. The result is a highly satisfactory profit for the investors and an attractive electricity price for all. This pilot case demonstrates the importance

³⁴ The buildings are spread over six plots belonging to different owners, encompassing (a) a road construction company, including electric trucks with solar recharging potential, and planning to optimize recharging in phase with the production of panels; (b) a storage hall hosting the main solar installation (1,38 MWp); (c) logistics and transport centre with electric trucks; (d) storage centre and workshop; (e) a private plot (not belonging to the FTI), whose owner has the economic interest to connect to the network; (f) cantonal green waste methanisation centre, called Pôle Bio with another large solar installation (800 kWp).

of solid public partnerships between FTI, SIG and companies, and highlights the potential for developing solar projects on industrial estates and large rooftops, and for grouping consumers around microgrids. On the other hand, it proves the difficult implementation of such a microgrid for three factors: (a) the ability to attract companies, particularly those with high consumption, which often benefit from attractive electricity prices; (b) ensuring a substantial level of self-consumption and, therefore, profitability, given that at the project's inception, the type and profile of future consumers were unknown, so the project was initiated without any guarantee of finding customers. Many companies, such as warehouses, have low electricity consumption; and (c) synchronising the solar installations and developing the microgrid alongside companies' construction projects.

FTI and SIG were pivotal actors in facilitating the public-private partnership in the creation of the REC. The FTI is a public foundation that locally represents the interests of the Canton of Geneva and the municipalities in the use of industrial sites. As the landowner of the industrial sites, it can require companies to participate in and connect to the solar microgrid through land use contracts and rights. Consequently, both the Canton of Geneva and the municipalities involved in industrial development are members of the Foundation Council, including the municipality of Satigny. In addition, SIG is the canton's industrial arm for developing energy projects. This company is jointly owned by the Canton of Geneva and its municipalities.

This means that cantonal and municipal interests are represented in the REC consortium by FTI and SIG. This has contributed to the development of an exemplary project not only profit-oriented.

In addition, territorial development legally requires the elaboration of a formal energy strategy defining key drivers for energy transition and low-carbon and concrete actions. Consequently, the energy master plan of ZIBAY has proven to be a central instrument in the development of the solar microgrid. All stakeholders were involved in the formulation of this vision: Canton of Geneva (through its Energy department), FTI, SIG and the Municipality of Satigny.

Establishing the ZIBAY solar microgrid community demonstrates the interaction between local, regional and national levels.

At the national level, the Federal Energy Act encourages self-consumers to form groups, bringing together self-producers and self-consumers from one or more neighbouring buildings to act as a single customer for the grid operator. The development of microgrids is allowed on adjacent land plots, even if they are separated by roads. The main financial lever is ensured by the Swiss government, which provides subsidies that generally cover 20% to 30% of the investment and have proved to be essential. In the case of ZIBAY, the project would not have been possible without this subsidy. The Federal Energy Act also obliges the grid operator

to purchase excess solar power at a minimum price (market price + guarantee of origin), which helps to make REC projects profitable.

The regional level plays an important role in the establishment of the ZIBAY solar microgrid community in three respects. Firstly, the Canton controls the application of the law, in particular, regarding the PV solar installations, which are mandatory for all new constructions. In the case study, although the solar installations are shared between the six industrial estates, no exemption was granted by the Canton to the individual industrial owners who had to meet the 10 W/m² requirement individually. Secondly, it issues building permits, provided that all legal requirements are met. Thirdly, in the specific context of this case study, the Canton is represented in the consortium through FTI (a cantonal foundation) and SIG, which is jointly owned by the canton (50%) and the municipalities (50%).

At the local level, the highly centralised Canton of Geneva leaves local municipalities with little room to influence the energy transition. They develop energy master plans that align with federal and cantonal energy policies. Some of them provide additional incentives for solar energy. They also play a key role in raising awareness among private actors on energy transition and facilitating public-private partnerships in energy projects. In the case of ZIBAY, for example, the municipality of Satigny has actively promoted and facilitated the energy transition strategy of this industrial area, which led to the creation of the solar microgrid project.

In conclusion, the Swiss Confederation clearly defines the responsibilities between the national, regional (cantonal) and local levels, providing a consistent regulatory framework for the implementation of RECs at the local level and proving the importance of public-private partnerships in facilitating such processes. The fact that this project is being carried out by public companies (FTI and SIG), which represent both regional (cantonal) and local (communal) interests, makes it an exemplary and successful project.

The ZIBAY REC project was made possible through a combination of bottom-up and top-down processes. On the one hand, there was the initiative of FTI and SIG in partnership with the industrial stakeholders. On the other hand, this project was aligned with the Geneva Energy Master Plan and was locally realised through the ZIBAY Energy Transition Master Plan. This project received support from both the Canton and the Municipality of Satigny.

Findings

The multilevel framework related to RECs in three European Regions

Based on a cross-cutting analysis of the three European regions presented in the previous section, it was possible to draw up a multilevel framework of authorities, regulations and tools related to the establishment and management of RECs in each region, as shown in *Table 1*.

Level	Piedmont, Italy	Andalusia, Spain	Geneve, Switzerland
National	<p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry for Environment and Energy Security Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment, 'ARERA' Energy Services Manager, 'GSE' <p><u>Regulations and tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (INECP), 2020 National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) LD 199/2021 and LD 210/2021 Ecological Transition Plan, 2022 MD 414/2024 	<p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge National Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving <p><u>Regulations and tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royal Decree-Law 23/2020 Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan 2021-2030 (INECP) Incentive Programme for Singular Pilot Projects of EC (CE IMPLEMENTA) National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) Programme of national financial support to community transformation offices (CE OFICINAS) National Strategy against Energy Poverty 2019-2024 	<p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communication (DETEC) Federal Office of Energy <p><u>Regulations and tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Federal Energy Strategy 2050 Swiss Federal Energy Law and Swiss Ordinance on Energy CO₂ Act Federal Act on the Security of Electricity Supply from Renewable Energy Sources Outreach activities from Federal Office of Energy Incentives from Pronovo (one-off payment for solar installations)
Regional	<p>Piedmont Region</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional council Sustainable Energy Development Department <p><u>Regulations and tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional Energy and Environmental Plan, 'PEAR' Regional Strategy for Climate Change 'SRCC' ROP ERDF, TO4 - Supporting the shift towards a low-carbon economy in all sectors LR 12/2018 on energy communities DGR 18-8520/2019 Next Generation You private fund LR 13/2021 on community cooperative 	<p>Autonomous Community of Andalusia</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional Ministry of Industry, Energy and Mines Andalusian Energy Agency <p><u>Regulations and tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Andalusian Energy Strategy Horizon 2030 (including REC programmes) Comprehensive Strategic Plan for the Elderly in Andalusia 2020-2023 Poverty Interreg Europe project ERDF 2014-2020. Objective T.O.4. Priority Line 4.c. 	<p>Canton of Geneva</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Canton Council Department of Youth, Environment and Safety Department of the Environment Directorate of Energy <p><u>Regulations and tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cantonal Energy Law Cantonal Land Use Master Plan Climate plan Cantonal incentives from the Building Program (for energy efficiency)
Provincial / inter-municipal	<p>Turin Metropolitan City</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metropolitan City of Turin Unions of municipalities <p><u>Tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Energy Action Plan of the Province of Turin (Metropolitan General Territorial Plan) 'Oil Free Zone' memorandum of understanding Temporary Association of Municipalities, 'ATS' Municipal SECAP 	<p>Granada</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provincial Council Granada Energy Agency <p><u>Tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate Change Adaptation Plan Shared Green Deal EU project Local Programme for the Just Energy Transition - Community Transformation Office National financial support to community transformation offices³⁵ 	<p>Neither intermediate nor regional institutional level in the Canton of Geneva</p>
Municipal	<p>Scalenghe (Turin)</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal council ATS Pinerolese <p><u>REC</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pinerolese Renewable Energy Community <p><u>Tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SECAP (Municipal Master Plan) <p>Sangano (Turin)</p> <p><u>REC</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sangano Common Energy Cooperative <p><u>Tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Municipal Master Plan) (SECAP under construction) Urban Strategy, 'SUA' 	<p>Seville</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal Department of Environment <p><u>REC</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Torreblanca Illumina <p><u>Tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SECAP Climate Change Municipal Plan Neighbourhood Plan – Zoning of Disadvantaged Areas <p>Monachil and Granada</p> <p><u>REC</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rio Monachil Energy Community Barrio de l'Alambra Energy Community <p><u>Tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project POCITYF – heritage contexts 	<p>Satigny</p> <p><u>Authorities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal council <p><u>REC</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZIBAY <p><u>Tools</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal land use master plan Municipal energy and climate master plan Energy master plan of ZIBAY <p>Nyon (Canton of Vaud)</p> <p><u>REC</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optima Solaire La Côte (solar cooperative)

Table 1 – Multilevel framework related to RECs in three European Regions, elaborated by the authors

³⁵ It is also present in the provinces of Cadiz, Cordoba, Almeria and in a group of small municipalities in the province of Sevilla.

The three countries analysed have national policies and regulations that focus on the relationship between energy and climate change as well as financial tools to incentivise the energy transition within the respective national development strategy. Despite the different political and administrative organisations, authorities, regulations and tools can be identified in all cases at the regional and municipal levels. In Switzerland, the provincial level is not directly represented, with the Cantonal level corresponding to both the regional and provincial levels, as will be widely illustrated later.

The interplay of local, regional and national levels in the establishment of RECs in the three case studies

As a result of the research on the three case studies, this section presents the interplay between the local, regional and national levels in the establishment of RECs in each region by highlighting the variable geometry of the common conceptual framework, in the different trajectories of REC establishment already introduced in *Figure 1*.

Figure 2 – Diagram of the multilevel framework in the Italian case. Elaborated by the authors

As shown in *Figure 2*, the Italian current national legal, regulatory and financial framework is complemented by the Piedmont Region's measures for the energy retrofitting of public buildings utilising the ERDF. Although the Piedmont Region has been a pioneer in setting up a regional legal framework for RECs, its role has ultimately proven to be technically and economically limited, supporting dissemination and commitment tasks. At the local level, municipalities may have a SECAP, which is often not coordinated with urban planning tools. Therefore, RECs emerge thanks to the bottom-up efforts of the local economic actors (mainly SMEs) and the civil society, as in the case of Sangano, or thanks to the institutional bottom-up efforts leading to soft intermunicipal cooperation, as exemplified by the *ATS Pinerolese*. It is worth mentioning that the cooperation between the municipalities of the Pinerolese area and their common energy transition and climate goals has been integrated into the joint SECAP (including 41 municipalities), which represents a common climate policy framework.

Conversely, the willingness of municipalities to collaborate as a REC has been disenchanted by the current legal and economic barriers, with integrated ESCO solutions proving more attractive to many municipalities. RECs are nationally incentivized, and their role can be further secured by municipalities, whose multifaceted role remains a subject of extensive debate.

Figure 3 – Diagram of the multilevel framework in the Spanish case. Elaborated by the authors

As shown in Figure 3, Spain has established a legal, regulatory and financial framework for RECs, which also targets vulnerable neighbourhoods that necessitate urban regeneration and the alleviation of energy poverty. The Spanish national level is in dialogue with the regional level, which is committed to energy and climate planning, protection of the elderly and vulnerable neighbourhoods. The region of Andalusia is a partner in European projects that provide funding for the implementation of actions with a social impact. On the other hand, at the local level, municipalities such as Seville, which has adopted a SECAP and is committed to achieving climate neutrality by 2030, lack the administrative capacity to participate in a REC with private entities. However, public surfaces for solar installations can be allocated as part of social initiatives. Several RECs are being activated by civil society organizations, directly involving residents in collective self-consumption configurations. The Spanish case shows that there is considerable cooperation between the national and regional levels. Indeed, the regions play a relevant role in the management of funds and in planning decisions, while the role of municipalities is still under debate, but to date it seems to be rather weak with respect to the development of RECs.

Figure 4 - Diagram of the multilevel framework in the Swiss case. Elaborated by the authors.

Based on Figure 4, Switzerland has a legal, regulatory and financial framework for RECs at the federal level, which is embedded in cantonal energy policy and related plans. These plans are combined with energy planning tools such as the municipal energy master plan, resulting in detailed energy master plans, as in the case of ZIBAY. Such a detailed master plan creates the conditions for the establishment of a multistakeholder consortium for REC investment and management, within a microgrid. At the local level, the REC is implemented and managed by the consortium of FTI, SIG and industrial partners, as foreseen by the decarbonisation of the industrial strategy implemented by both the canton and the municipality. The Swiss case clearly shows that effective multilevel governance of the establishment of RECs establishment and the energy transition can ensure the successful implementation of projects.

As RECs are defined and regulated at the European level and at the federal level in Switzerland, unsurprisingly, the national governments always provide comprehensive legal, financial and regulatory frameworks for their development and implementation.

The regional level proves to be more influential in countries where regions also possess a greater degree of autonomy. For example, in Spain, the Autonomous Community of Andalusia has a regional policy for energy transition, for the elderly and vulnerable neighbourhoods. In the Swiss Confederation, the cantons have cantonal laws and master plans for the energy transition, while in Italy, in regions with limited autonomy such as Piedmont, the main competence is focused on ERDF management, but not directly on energy planning.

The most diverse role in the establishment of RECs is that of the municipalities. Municipalities can play a leading role or be confined to a supporting role. Municipalities may or may not be REC members, and they may or may not provide public surfaces for solar installations. Furthermore, municipalities may or may not integrate energy transition policy in urban planning and support RECs within predefined policy frameworks such as SECAPs or Climate Neutrality 2030 initiatives.

Discussion

The multilevel framework

At the regional level, the three cases show a range of planning, legal and regulatory provisions related to energy, environment, climate change and low-carbon economy, with an active role of agencies, active departments and directorates focused on energy. This proves that energy issues typically require a regional dimension, although the energy and climate planning tools identified at the regional level, may or may not be consistent with regional spatial planning tools.

The provincial level is rather differentiated. In fact, for Italian cities such as Turin, which are regional capitals, the province coincides with the metropolitan city, which has a metropolitan Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP) and a metropolitan strategic spatial plan. In Andalusia, the provincial level can play an influential role such as in the case of Granada, where the Provincial Energy Agency provides direct support to municipal initiatives, including pioneering projects such as the establishment of RECs in historic neighbourhoods. In terms of the tools at their disposal, the city of Granada has a Climate Change Adaptation Plan, and the Community Transformation Offices are working on a just energy transition. As already mentioned, the Swiss case lacks the provincial level.

At the municipal level, all cases show direct municipal involvement in energy action planning. This is evident in the definition and implementation of SECAPs in Italy and Spain, and in communal energy master plans in Switzerland. Municipalities can back RECs by providing support in their definition and start-up, directly with the participation in a REC, or placing public surfaces at their disposal for installations dedicated to collective self-consumption.

As *Table 1* clearly demonstrates, higher levels typically support the creation of RECs by allocating financial resources and establishing overall regulations, whereas intermediate levels are expected to play a significant role in aligning climate and energy policy at the territorial level. As direct contributors to climate and energy policy, municipalities play an active role in promoting, establishing and setting up RECs, including legal establishment, localisation, and building installations.

The activation of RECs

Although RECs can be activated without the participation of public local authorities, this paper presents evidence to suggest that the role of public entities is substantial for at least two reasons: (i) REC activation is facilitated by clear, consistent and complete regulations, as well as effective planning and financial tools, (ii) as local development initiatives, RECs unavoidably interact with municipal policies and urban planning. Arguably, a bidirectional relationship exists between RECs and the local public policy sector resulting in a convergence between institutional provisions and bottom-up initiatives. From this perspective, the public

role, and eventually, the public leadership in the establishment process of RECs, is expressed in a number of ways: (i) in terms of inter-municipal cooperation dedicated to creating such a territorial REC as with the ATS Pinerolese, (ii) the late integration of the municipal authority in a REC created by local economic actors, as with Sangano, and (iii) the leading of the regional and provincial energy agencies in Sevilla Torreblanca and Granada, respectively, particularly with regard to technical issues, as opposed to municipalities being confined to providing public surfaces for PV installations.

The Italian case demonstrates the pivotal role of national financial support for small municipalities in energy initiatives. The small size of many Italian municipalities is important for several reasons. (i) Firstly, a single municipal government may lack the financial, technical and human resources necessary for energy and climate initiatives beyond traditional land-use and environmental municipal management. (ii) Secondly, small size often makes it impossible to achieve economies of scale. (iii) Soft interinstitutional arrangements, such as territorial memoranda of understanding or temporary associations of public authorities, are essential to ensure territorial cooperation and synergies. Such cooperation enables more compelling results to be achieved, not least for technical reasons such as the inclusion of more than one municipality in the same electricity substation. In both the *ATS Pinerolese* and *Sangano Energia Comune* case studies, the municipalities have played a crucial role in stakeholder engagement and dissemination by raising awareness of the benefits of establishing a REC. However, current legal barriers and the uncertain Italian legal framework have limited the possibility of a public-led REC initiative in both cases. In Sangano, this ended in a community cooperative led by private SMEs, and the *ATS Pinerolese* is an association with no current or potential REC activities.

Regardless of the size of the municipality, the Italian case also highlights a mismatch between climate/energy and spatial planning policies. In other words, urban plans do not consistently or widely integrate energy and climate actions. This is partly because the boundaries of the implementation of different sectoral policies do not coincide. This lack of integration undermines the achievement of climate goals, which would require the implementation of more comprehensive territorial development projects.

Although less lucrative in terms of social benefits, one viable option is the participation foundation chosen by the Municipality of Villafranca, eventually supported by an ESCO. Another option is the community cooperative, as in the case of Sangano. This option is closer to REC's common goals and social purposes, allows for the subsequent participation of the municipality, and does not require municipal leadership. However, Piedmont Region has decided not to shoulder the cost of technical and legal feasibility studies, unlike other Italian Regions³⁶. Instead, this expense has been entrusted to private sponsors such as the Compagnia

³⁶ Emilia Romagna and Veneto, for example, acknowledged the need and issued a call for funding to financially support the public and/or private RECs' activation process within the regional territories.

di San Paolo. This is happening despite Piedmont being a pioneer in regional support for REC activation, as it was the first regional jurisdiction to pass legislation on this subject. However, none of the modalities introduced by the regional law have been implemented. Regardless of the regional guidelines, which remain on paper, all RECs under construction merely adhere only to the national rules and guidelines.

In terms of addressing the social issue of energy poverty, Spain is the only country with a national strategy, namely the National Strategy Against Energy Poverty 2019-2024. Italy established the National Observatory for Energy Poverty in 2022; however, the Observatory plays no active role in the promotion and activation of RECs. Switzerland does not have a relevant energy poverty policy, but it is possible that energy vulnerability is underestimated and more widespread than previously thought (Hearn et al, 2022).

Consistent with the national strategy against energy poverty, the Andalusian region plays a fundamental role in social policies targeting the elderly, supported by European funds. Unsurprisingly, *Torreblanca Ilumina* was established to reduce energy poverty. At the national level, the NIECP acknowledges the role of RECs and, in line with the NextGenerationEU fund, ensures national incentives (*CE IMPLEMENTA*) and financial aid for Community Transformation Offices to promote and activate RECs (*CE OFICINAS*). These policies are implemented by the Andalusian Energy Agency within the Andalusian Energy Strategy 2030. Regional participation occurs through the agency, which engages with local stakeholders via the *Powerty Interreg Europe*, a key driver in the activation of the Torreblanca Illumina. The designation of the Torreblanca neighbourhood as a vulnerable area is a regional responsibility.

Notably, in Torreblanca, the electricity distributor prevented solar installations from being connected to the grid due to an unclear regulatory framework that made the process uncertain. In Switzerland, such criticality can affect solar cooperatives. For example, Demain la Côte, located in the Canton of Vaud, developed independently from electricity distributors. This illustrates a duality of bottom-up processes from the private sector and top-down processes from institutions. The question that arises is to what extent RECs should depend on the regulatory framework, and whether this framework should evolve to include such local initiatives. In Switzerland, for example, Local Electricity Communities (LECs) have emerged and could potentially replace cooperatives. Arguably, the regulatory framework should evolve in line with the development of new initiatives.

Furthermore, the Spanish case considers collective self-consumption plants at the neighbourhood level. Installing one large plant to provide energy to adjacent consumers optimises investment and enables families and groups who cannot afford to install their own plants to benefit as consumers. Moreover, this plant could be funded through public funds or crowdfunding, enabling low-income families to be consumers at a discounted price or even for free. Indeed, in Spain, several families are vulnerable to energy poverty, which is a significant

social problem for civil society organisations that typically operate in vulnerable contexts. Consequently, these organisations play a pivotal role in promoting community-based renewable energy production and consumption, achieving the redistribution of social benefits. Notably, Seville's Torreblanca neighbourhood, which is undergoing urban regeneration, has been recognized as a disadvantaged area in local planning. This development creates the fundamental conditions for the legitimate establishment of a REC as a driver of urban regeneration and development.

In terms of policy implementation, Andalusia exemplifies the pivotal role of technical entities such as public energy agencies. In Granada, for example, the energy agency is responsible for liaising with municipalities and the region, as well as ensuring consistent information dissemination among municipalities. This is particularly relevant for smaller municipalities, which lack the internal resources to effectively implement energy and climate policies, including the preparation of SECAPs, as was observed also in the Italian case. Finally, the Andalusian experience highlights a critical issue: municipalities must comply with the regional request to prepare municipal climate change plans and SECAPs to ensure they meet the legal conditions to receive European grants. This means that each municipality has two parallel tools for the same topics: one to comply with the national planning framework and another to comply with European policy. This creates an unnecessary and misleading duplication.

By contrast, Switzerland demonstrates that the structured integration of urban and energy/climate actions can be achieved through planning tools. Specifically, municipal master plans cover energy-related issues alongside urban planning for climate change adaptation. Within the Swiss multilevel integrated framework, it is the municipalities that drive the energy transition through small-scale solar energy production and community initiatives. The Swiss case demonstrated that energy communities can be a powerful local response to the overall challenge of energy transition. On the other hand, cooperatives are trans-local energy-sharing organisations. These cooperatives facilitate the formation of distant/virtual solar communities, where all produced energy is fed into the Distribution System Operator (DSO) grid, with any additional profits being reinvested in new installations. Citizens, public authorities, companies, associations and other organisations can participate in such projects by purchasing a share in the cooperative's capital.

The Swiss case is particularly significant due to the possibility of organising an energy community within a microgrid. This is essentially an island placed just inside one municipal area and set up within the national electricity grid. It is devoted to the functioning of a specific energy community. More generally, the current Swiss political debate highlights a critical factor: the degree of proximity among REC participants. Swiss regulation is evolving to facilitate mutualization among distant buildings.

In Geneva, SIG is responsible for the technical installation, maintenance and operation of the microgrid under a service contract. A consortium has been set up, bringing together six industrial partners to pool their self-consumption of solar energy, and specific regulations have been drawn up to handle the contractual aspects between the partners. This development was made possible by the public leadership of FTI, which owns the industrial land and invested independently of financial risk compensated by such legal constraints. As the landowner, FTI can require other companies to connect to the microgrid as part of the land rights, providing significant legal leverage. FTI and SIG have been identified as pivotal actors in facilitating the public-private partnership that led to the creation of the REC. The Canton of Geneva, as well as the municipalities involved, such as Satigny, are members of the Foundation Council. SIG is owned by the Canton of Geneva and its municipalities for the development of energy projects at the territorial level.

Conclusion and avenues for future research

This paper provides critical insights into the role of RECs as emerging policy instruments within the broader framework of the European energy transition. Drawing on comparative case studies from Piedmont (Italy), Andalusia (Spain), and Geneva (Switzerland), the analysis underscores the significance of multilevel governance and institutional design in enabling or constraining the development of RECs.

RECs are not merely technical solutions for local energy generation, i.e. they represent complex, multi-actor governance mechanisms that embody the principles of decentralization, participatory democracy, and social innovation. As policy instruments, RECs function through a combination of agreement-based governance mechanisms and incentive structures, positioning them as tools that link state policy objectives with grassroots initiatives. RECs operate at the intersection of energy policy, spatial planning, and social equity. Their design and implementation are shaped by legal, institutional, and fiscal frameworks that vary significantly across national and regional contexts. In this light, RECs can be understood as flexible instruments of public policy, whose effectiveness depends on several interlocking factors. The implementation of the energy transition requires territorial public action, with the diverse European institutional arrangements exerting a significant influence on this process. These arrangements demonstrate that greater regional autonomy is associated with a higher degree of RECs' implementation.

Regions and municipalities are progressively assuming the role of primary energy and climate policymakers, as evidenced by Poupeau & Boutaud (2021). However, an in-depth investigation of their role reveals a multifaceted array of possibilities that necessitate further comprehensive analysis in subsequent research endeavours. This is also demonstrated by Urban et al (2025), who revised 433 abstracts inquiring about the dominant perspective over RECs used by researchers. They found that a technical perspective dominates over a social and

institutional one. Further studies on the capacity of RECs in reducing energy poverty, increasing social equality and hampering energy segregation are highly recommended.

More in general, the paper builds on a comparative analysis of institutional influences from different regions, bridging governance dynamics with the practical challenges of energy transition, offering insights that are broadly applicable across governance contexts. Therefore, this study has contributed to discuss (i) to what extent RECs can be developed just as the local implementation of a national policy, given a widely varied configurations of regional and municipal power structures, i.e. authorities and policy instruments; (ii) the potential development of RECs in the absent or insufficient integration of spatial and energy planning tools, given the contribution that RECs could ensure to the achievement of sustainable development objectives; (iii) the role of different stakeholders in promoting the social benefits produced by RECs, and their fair and equal redistribution; (iv) to what extent it is acceptable to include the reduction of energy poverty among the potential social benefits achievable by the establishment of a REC; (v) the setting of proper financial investments for different scales and organisation of RECs' initiatives, with public or private leadership; and (vi) a varied policy regulating the RECs' establishment and development, given the coexistence of radically diverse agents, ranging from the industrial to the third sector over the European regional territories.

Drawing from three distinct cases in terms of governance structures, this study paves the way for future research, particularly exploring the interplay between energy transition processes and governance frameworks. Empirical evidence has demonstrated that decentralised governance arrangements have been more effective in integrating spatial planning with climate and energy strategies. This, in turn, has enabled the achievement of critical energy transition objectives through the activation of RECs, as illustrated by the Swiss case.

Municipal governments play a pivotal role in facilitating the establishment of RECs, however, their effective activation is significantly dependent on supportive national and regional funding mechanisms as well as enabling regulations. Furthermore, citizen participation is identified as a fundamental element in the successful activation of RECs, ensuring that the social dimension of the energy transition is not only acknowledged but also strengthened.

From a policy perspective, the strategic activation of RECs as a policy instrument offers a promising pathway to accelerate the overall energy transition policy while fostering community empowerment and inclusivity. To this end, policymakers should focus on creating frameworks that encourage collaboration among multiple levels of government, provide accessible funding instruments, and promote citizen engagement to maximize the potential of RECs. By aligning governance models with the principles of decentralization, inclusivity, and sustainability, RECs can serve as transformative policy instruments to address the dual

challenges of energy transition and social equity and, in so doing, the achievement of a range of environmental and social development objectives.

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Conflict of interest

None.

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